

ENDOVASCULAR REPAIR OF INFRARENAL ABDOMINAL AORTIC ANEURYSM AND TYPE OF ENDOLEAK

*Mohammed As'ad, Khaldoun Alwreikat, Omar Madadha, Thair Altrabsheh, Mosaab Alquwaider

India.

*Corresponding Author: Mohammed As'ad

India.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18796203>

How to cite this Article: *Mohammed As'ad, Khaldoun Alwreikat, Omar Madadha, Thair Altrabsheh, Mosaab Alquwaider (2026). Endovascular Repair Of Infrarenal Abdominal Aortic Aneurysm And Type Of Endoleak. European Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 13(3), 96–100.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

Article Received on 31/01/2026

Article Revised on 20/02/2026

Article Published on 01/03/2026

ABSTRACT

Objective: The current study aimed to explore endoleaks events post-EVAR, and find relations with clinical and procedure characteristics from medical records. **Methods:** A retrospective design analyzed patients undergoing EVAR for AAA. Study was conducted in King Hussein Medical Center (KHMC). Data was collected for demographics, surgical, and clinical variables. Data collection started from January 2019 till August 2025.

Results: The participants consisted of 111 subjects with an average age of 72.03 ± 9.29 years; 92.79 were males, 29.73 had diabetes mellitus, 66.67 were hypertensive, and 62.16 were smokers. The endoleak group ($n=241$) had a greater aneurysm size than those without ($n=871$) (7.06 ± 1.90 vs 6.07 ± 1.00 cm; $p=0.007$). The longer hospital stays were more prevalent among the participants with endoleak. The prevalence of hypertension was higher among the endoleak group (83.33% vs 62.07; $p=0.050$). Endoleak types were exclusively present in the endoleak group: Type 1 (54.17%; $p<0.001$), Type 2 (58.33%; $p<0.001$), and Type 3 (12.50%; $p=0.009$). Follow-up endoleaks at 6 months were significantly more common in those with baseline endoleak (17.39% vs 0%; $p=0.006$).

Conclusion: We studied in this cohort the presentation of these endoleaks in relation to patient profiles and procedural details. Bigger size aneurysms and longer stays at the ICU were reported in patients who experienced endoleaks. In patients who developed endoleaks, hypertension was an important risk factor presented in these patients. Type II endoleaks were the most common seen type, as well as follow-up endoleaks at 6 months were more common in those with baseline endoleak.

KEYWORDS: EVAR, abdominal aortic aneurysm, endoleak, infrarenal aneurysm, Jordan.

INTRODUCTION

Abdominal aortic aneurysm (AAA) is defined as abnormally dilated infrarenal abdominal aorta of 3 centimeters or greater.^[1] Risk factors include smoking, male gender, hypertension, people older than 65-year-old, coronary artery disease and a previous family history of AAA. Most AAAs clinically present asymptomatic unless they rupture.^[2] AAAs remain a serious threat to worldwide healthcare, with higher death rates when they rupture.^[3] Etiology of AAA includes alterations in the aortic wall structure such as adventitia and media thinning because of extracellular matrix degradation and vascular smooth muscle loss.^[4] Aneurysms usually occur along the aorta. However, they are mostly found in the infrarenal region. Ultrasound screening remains a cost-effective and efficient way to prevent rupture of aortic

aneurysm.^[5] According to the clinical guidelines of the treatment of AAA patients established by European Society for Vascular Surgery (ESVS), endovascular repair (EVAR) is one of the recommended treatments for anatomically suitable infrarenal AAAs.^[6] Furthermore, EVAR nowadays are not only limited to infrarenal AAA but also extend to include other AAA types like juxtarenal AAA, and thoraco-abdominal aneurysms.^[7] Endoleaks are common and affect almost thirty percent of patients managed by EVAR and can cause sac enlargement and higher risk of rupture is noted among these patients. Long-term monitoring by a multidisciplinary team is essential for the treatment of EVAR patients.^[8] Endoleaks are reported more frequently after fenestrated/branched endovascular aneurysm repair (F/B-EVAR) compared to infrarenal

EVAR due to the length of component junctions numbers and the length of aortic coverage.^[9] Behavior and incidence of endoleaks usually vary between ruptured (r-EVAR) and elective EVAR (e-EVAR). For example, all endoleaks were more common in e-EVAR patients than in r-EVAR patients.^[10]

Local data lacks a complete understanding of how these endoleaks present and behave in relation to patients' characteristics and type of procedure. So, in this study we aim to describe the endoleaks found after EVAR in our center and to look at how the different types relate to the basic clinical and procedural characteristics available in our clinical records.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

Study design

This study was a retrospective cross-sectional analysis conducted among 111 patients who underwent EVAR for infrarenal AAAs. The study aimed to study the endoleaks found after EVAR in our center and to look at how the different types relate to the basic clinical and procedural characteristics available in our records. Data were collected from clinical health records of patients managed at King Hussein Medical Center (KHMC) from January 2019 to August 2025.

Patients, clinical assessments, and data collection

A total of 111 patients who underwent EVAR procedure for infrarenal AAAs were included in the study. Demographic variables included age and gender. We extracted several clinical information such as associated comorbidities and risk factors (diabetes mellitus, hypertension, smoking status, anticoagulant use). Type of procedure (elective vs emergency) was also studied. We also focused on aneurysm size, presence of iliac occlusion, presence and type of endoleak, and endoleak presence during follow-up (1 month, 3 months, and 6 months).

The examination duration was between January 2019 and August 2025. All extracted information was recorded in a structured database for subsequent statistical analysis.

Ethical Consideration

This study approval was waived by the Institutional Review Board at King Hussein Medical Center (KHMC). This study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki (1964), and approval was obtained before data collection.

Statistical Analysis

Continuous variables were summarized as mean \pm standard deviation and compared between groups using the Wilcoxon rank-sum test. Categorical variables were reported as counts and percentages and assessed using Pearson's Chi-squared or Fisher's exact tests, as appropriate. All tests were two-sided, and p-values <0.05 were considered statistically significant.

RESULT

The participants consisted of 111 subjects with an average age of 72.03 ± 9.29 years; 92.79 were males, 29.73 had diabetes mellitus, 66.67 were hypertensive, and 62.16 were smokers (Table 1). The majority of procedures were elective (76.58%), as well as 21.62% were at baseline. The mean size of aneurysm was 6.28 ± 1.30 cm, and the iliac occlusion was seen in 39.05%. Most ICU stays were 1 day (79.82%). The duplex findings of lower limbs were normal in 80.39 and 16.67 respectively showed shrinkage. Endoleaks are discovered in the 1-month (1.14), 3-month (1.75), and 6-month (5.00) follow-up.

The endoleak group (n=241) had a greater aneurysm size than those without (n=871) (7.06 ± 1.90 vs 6.07 ± 1.00 cm; $p=0.007$) (Table 2). There were significant differences in the distributions of ICU stay (global $p=0.002$), where the longer stay durations were more prevalent among the participants with endoleak. The prevalence of hypertension was higher among the endoleak group (83.33% vs 62.07; $p=0.050$). They also found no significant differences in terms of age ($p=0.2$), sex ($p=0.2$), diabetes ($p=0.3$), smoking ($p=0.4$), anticoagulant use (>0.9), type of procedure ($p=0.5$) and the classification of lower limb duplex ($p=0.2$).

Endoleak types were exclusively present in the endoleak group: Type 1 (54.17%; $p<0.001$), Type 2 (58.33%; $p<0.001$), and Type 3 (12.50%; $p=0.009$). Follow-up endoleaks at 6 months were significantly more common in those with baseline endoleak (17.39% vs 0%; $p=0.006$) (Table 2).

Table 1: Baseline Demographic, Clinical, Procedural, and Follow-up Characteristics.

Characteristic	N = 111 ^f
Age	72.03 (9.29)
Gender	
Female	8 (7.21%)
Male	103 (92.79%)
Diabetes Mellitus	33 (29.73%)
Hypertension	74 (66.67%)
Smoking	69 (62.16%)
Anticoagulant Use	23 (20.72%)
Type of Procedure	
Elective	85 (76.58%)
Emergency	26 (23.42%)
Have Endoleak	24 (21.62%)
Type of Endoleak	
Type 1	13 (11.71%)
Type 2	14 (12.61%)
Type 3	3 (2.70%)
Aneurysm Size	6.28 (1.30)
Iliac Occlusion	41 (39.05%)
ICU Period	
1	87 (79.82%)
2	11 (10.09%)
3	8 (7.34%)

4	1 (0.92%)
5	1 (0.92%)
6	1 (0.92%)
Lower Limb Duplex	
Increase	3 (2.94%)
Normal	82 (80.39%)
Shrinkage	17 (16.67%)
Endoleak During Follow Up	
1 Month FU	1 (1.14%)
3 Months FU	1 (1.75%)
6 Months FU	4 (5.00%)
¹ Mean (SD); n (%)	

Table 2: Comparison of Demographic, Clinical, Procedural, and Follow-up Characteristics Between Participants With and Without Endoleak.

Characteristic	No Endoleak N = 87 ¹	Had Endoleak N = 24 ¹	p-value ²	Overall N = 111 ¹
Age	72.39 (9.72)	70.71 (7.61)	0.2	72.03 (9.29)
Aneurysm Size	6.07 (1.00)	7.06 (1.90)	0.007	6.28 (1.30)
ICU Period			0.002	
1	74 (87.06%)	13 (54.17%)		87 (79.82%)
2	5 (5.88%)	6 (25.00%)		11 (10.09%)
3	4 (4.71%)	4 (16.67%)		8 (7.34%)
4	1 (1.18%)	0 (0.00%)		1 (0.92%)
5	0 (0.00%)	1 (4.17%)		1 (0.92%)
6	1 (1.18%)	0 (0.00%)		1 (0.92%)
Gender			0.2	
Female	8 (9.20%)	0 (0.00%)		8 (7.21%)
Male	79 (90.80%)	24 (100.00%)		103 (92.79%)
Diabetes Mellitus	24 (27.59%)	9 (37.50%)	0.3	33 (29.73%)
Hypertension	54 (62.07%)	20 (83.33%)	0.050	74 (66.67%)
Smoking	56 (64.37%)	13 (54.17%)	0.4	69 (62.16%)
Anticoagulant Use	18 (20.69%)	5 (20.83%)	>0.9	23 (20.72%)
Type of Procedure			0.5	
Elective	68 (78.16%)	17 (70.83%)		85 (76.58%)
Emergency	19 (21.84%)	7 (29.17%)		26 (23.42%)
Type of Endoleak				
Type 1	0 (0.00%)	13 (54.17%)	<0.001	13 (11.71%)
Type 2	0 (0.00%)	14 (58.33%)	<0.001	14 (12.61%)
Type 3	0 (0.00%)	3 (12.50%)	0.009	3 (2.70%)
Lower Limb Duplex			0.2	
Increase	1 (1.28%)	2 (8.33%)		3 (2.94%)
Normal	65 (83.33%)	17 (70.83%)		82 (80.39%)
Shrinkage	12 (15.38%)	5 (20.83%)		17 (16.67%)
Endoleak During Follow Up				
1 Month FU	0 (0.00%)	1 (5.26%)	0.2	1 (1.14%)
3 Months FU	0 (0.00%)	1 (7.14%)	0.2	1 (1.75%)
6 Months FU	0 (0.00%)	4 (17.39%)	0.006	4 (5.00%)
¹ Mean (SD); n (%)				
² Wilcoxon rank sum test; Fisher's exact test; Pearson's Chi-squared test				

DISCUSSION

Abdominal aortic aneurysms (AAA) usually present asymptomatic and are found in approximately six percent of men and 1.7% of women who are older than 65 years.^[11] The pathophysiology of AAA is linked to an underlying arterial injury resulting in inflammation cascade and breakdown of extracellular matrix protein by

proteinases, weakening the arterial wall.^[12] Endovascular aneurysm repair (EVAR) is considered a standard option in managing AAA in men with 5.5 cm aneurysm and 5.0 cm aneurysm or more in women.^[13] Currently, imaging surveillance for small aneurysms and surgical treatment for large, ruptured and symptomatic are the techniques used to manage AAA.^[14] One of the most common issues

seen on follow-up imaging is endoleaks after endovascular repair.^[8] Endoleaks are leaks into the aneurysm sac, occurring after the EVAR procedure. They are usually detected following graft implantation and suggest unsuccessful treatment.^[15] There are five subtypes of endoleaks, and each type has a specific management. Type I is the most dangerous, whereas type II endoleaks are the most prevalent.^[15]

In this study, we aimed to describe the endoleaks identified after EVAR in our center and to look at how the various types relate to the basic clinical and procedural characteristics available in our records.

Our cohort reviewed 111 patients underwent EVAR for infrarenal AAA at King Hussein Medical Center (KHMC). Most of the patients were males (92.79%). Smoking was reported in 62.16% of patients in our cohort, 29.73% had diabetes mellitus, and 66.67% were hypertensive. In a recent systematic review, the authors highlighted many factors related to AAA. The results revealed that smoking, male gender, older age, and comorbidities like hypertension, obesity, hypercholesterolemia, and cardiovascular diseases are main predictors related to AAA.^[16] Additionally, EVAR surgeries are chosen electively rather than as an emergent procedure.^[17] Which is in agreement with the findings in the current study, in which, 76.58% of the reported procedures were elective. In our cohorts, endoleaks were reported in 21.62% of patients. Most of them had type II endoleaks. This is consistent with several studies in literature stating that type II endoleaks are the most prevalent endoleak type following EVAR. Their course varies from indolent to self-limiting, however, others might lead to aneurysm rupture.^[18] The endoleak group in our cohort had a greater aneurysm size than those without. AAA size is an important predictor of complications like endoleaks. Patients with larger aneurysms were more likely to have late complications and reduced survival rates.^[19] Longer hospital stays were more common among endoleaks patients in our cohort. Moreover, the prevalence of hypertension was higher among the endoleak group (83.33%) in this cohort. A recent retrospective study confirmed that hypertension is a common comorbidity (70%) seen among patients who underwent EVAR.^[20] EVAR advantages over open AAA repair include shorter stays in the intensive care unit (ICU) and hospital.^[21]

The main limitation of this study is its retrospective design, as well as limited population size. Additionally, the study was a single-center study and involved all AAA repairs from January 2019 to August 2025. Only patients with comprehensive data were involved in this cohort, hence the study's retrospective design may have caused selection bias. The study's single-center design has contributed to limiting its application to larger centers or various patient populations. Some patients with inadequate follow-up data were excluded, which in turn can bias the outcomes reported. The present study's

strength lies in providing practical information and center-specific data over a reliable follow-up period.

We encourage future research to develop prospective, multicenter studies with longer follow-up periods to enhance the understanding of various types of endoleaks.

CONCLUSION

Endovascular repair has emerged as the standard intervention for the treatment of infrarenal AAAs because of reduced morbidity and mortality, and better outcomes. However, there are possible adverse effects that should be acknowledged after EVAR procedure such as different types of endoleaks. We studied in this cohort the presentation of these endoleaks in relation to patient profiles and procedural details. Bigger size aneurysms and longer stays at the ICU were reported in patients who experienced endoleaks. In patients who developed endoleaks, hypertension was an important risk factor presented in these patients. Type II endoleaks were the most common seen type, as well as follow-up endoleaks at 6 months were more common in those with baseline endoleak.

REFERENCES

1. Y K, K H, S L, P G, N G, M A. Abdominal aortic aneurysm: pictorial review of common appearances and complications. *Annals of translational medicine* [Internet], 2017 Jun [cited 2025 Nov 27]; 5(12). Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28706924/>
2. Haque K, Bhargava P. Abdominal Aortic Aneurysm, 2022; 106(2).
3. A M, N E, J W, D H, Hb N, K R, et al. Trends in Abdominal Aortic Aneurysm Repair Incidence, Comorbidity, Treatment, and Mortality: A Danish Nationwide Cohort Study, 1996-2018. *Clinical epidemiology* [Internet]. 2024 Mar 13 [cited 2025 Nov 27]; 16. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/38505359/>
4. Sakalihan N, Michel JB, Katsargyris A, Kuivaniemi H, Defraigne JO, Nchimi A, et al. Abdominal aortic aneurysms. *Nat Rev Dis Primers*, 2018 Oct 18; 4(1): 34.
5. Wang LJ, Prabhakar AM, Kwolek CJ. Current status of the treatment of infrarenal abdominal aortic aneurysms. *Cardiovascular Diagnosis and Therapy*, 2018 Apr; 8(Suppl 1): S191-S19S199.
6. A W, I VH, F BG, S BM, X B, Jr B, et al. Editor's Choice -- European Society for Vascular Surgery (ESVS) 2024 Clinical Practice Guidelines on the Management of Abdominal Aorto-Iliac Artery Aneurysms. *European journal of vascular and endovascular surgery: the official journal of the European Society for Vascular Surgery* [Internet]. 2024 Feb [cited 2025 Nov 27]; 67(2). Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/38307694/>
7. Teraa M, Hazenberg CEVB. The Current Era of Endovascular Aortic Interventions and What the

- Future Holds. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*, 2022 Jan; 11(19): 5900.
8. Cifuentes S, Mendes BC, Tabiei A, Scali ST, Oderich GS, DeMartino RR. Management of Endoleaks After Elective Infrarenal Aortic Endovascular Aneurysm Repair. [cited 2025 Nov 27]; Available from: <https://jamanetwork.com/journals/jamasurgery/fullarticle/2807722>
 9. Marecki HL, Finnesgard EJ, Nuvvula S, Nguyen TT, Boitano LT, Jones DW, et al. Characterization and management of type II and complex endoleaks after fenestrated/branched endovascular aneurysm repair. *Journal of Vascular Surgery*, 2023 Jul 1; 78(1): 29–37.
 10. Quinn AA, Mehta M, Teymouri MJ, Keenan ME, Paty PSK, Zhou Y, et al. The incidence and fate of endoleaks vary between ruptured and elective endovascular abdominal aortic aneurysm repair. *Journal of Vascular Surgery*, 2017 Jun 1; 65(6): 1617–24.
 11. S DF, N D, J F. Infrarenal Abdominal Aortic Aneurysm. *The Surgical clinics of North America* [Internet]. 2023 Aug [cited 2025 Dec 14]; 103(4). Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/37455027/>
 12. Abdominal aortic aneurysms. *Progress in Cardiovascular Diseases*, 2021 Mar 1; 65: 34–43.
 13. Schanzer A, Oderich GS. Management of Abdominal Aortic Aneurysms. *New England Journal of Medicine* [Internet]. 2021 Oct 28 [cited 2025 Dec 14]; Available from: <https://www.nejm.org/doi/abs/10.1056/NEJMcp2108504>
 14. Golledge J, Thanigaimani S, Powell JT, Tsao PS. Pathogenesis and management of abdominal aortic aneurysm. *Eur Heart J.*, 2023 Aug 1; 44(29): 2682–97.
 15. Vr Y, Ss S, Sl V, S A, R M, R SN, et al. The Challenge of Endoleaks in Endovascular Aneurysm Repair (EVAR): A Review of Their Types and Management. *Cureus* [Internet], 2023 May 31 [cited 2025 Dec 14]; 15(5). Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/37398777/>
 16. Song P, He Y, Adeloje D, Zhu Y, Ye X, Yi Q, et al. The Global and Regional Prevalence of Abdominal Aortic Aneurysms: A Systematic Review and Modeling Analysis. *Annals of Surgery*, 2022 Sep 30; 277(6): 912.
 17. Capó XF, Reyes MEG, Cánovas ÁS, Besalduch LS, Ruiz DF, Montoya SB, et al. Hospital Volume of Elective Abdominal Aortic Aneurysm Repair as a Predictor of Mortality After Ruptured Abdominal Aortic Aneurysm Repair. *European Journal of Vascular and Endovascular Surgery*, 2024 Jul 1; 68(1): 30–8.
 18. Chen JX, Stavropoulos SW. Type 2 Endoleak Management. *Semin Intervent Radiol*, 2020 Oct; 37(04): 365–70.
 19. Pj W, O G, J H, K S, J W. Effect of AAA Size on Mortality and Morbidity After Endovascular Aortic Repair. *Journal of clinical medicine* [Internet]. 2025 Aug 15 [cited 2025 Dec 15]; 14(16). Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/40869612/>
 20. Avabde D, Miah MMR, Alnatsheh W, Chong PL, Butt A, Avabde D, et al. Feasibility and Safety of Endovascular Aneurysm Repair (EVAR) in a District General Hospital: A Retrospective Study of 10-Year Outcomes. *Cureus* [Internet]. 2024 Oct 29 [cited 2025 Dec 15]; 16. Available from: <https://cureus.com/articles/312214-feasibility-and-safety-of-endovascular-aneurysm-repair-evar-in-a-district-general-hospital-a-retrospective-study-of-10-year-outcomes>
 21. Gavali H, Mani K, Tegler G, Kawati R, Covaciu L, Wanhainen A. Editor's Choice – Prolonged ICU Length of Stay after AAA Repair: Analysis of Time Trends and Long-term Outcome. *European Journal of Vascular and Endovascular Surgery*, 2017 Aug 1; 54(2): 157–63.